

THE TRAINING SESSION GROUP IS FOCUSED ON DEVELOPING THE MOVEMENT SKILLS AND ABILITIES OF LONG-DISTANCE RUNNERS DURING THE TRAINING PROCESS

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Annotation: This article presents key tools used in preparing long-distance runners within a training group by correctly distributing annual training plans, monitoring physiological processes occurring in the athletes' bodies, and applying workloads appropriate to their work capacity. The goal is to help athletes achieve high performance in competitions. Practical research and methodological recommendations in this field emphasize that the physical development and preparedness of long-distance runners are closely linked to biological and physiological processes. The methodological tools used during training are essential for studying the means and methods applied in training long-distance runners. A comprehensive approach to preparing skilled athletes-considering training loads, rest intervals, and their physiological processes-has a positive effect on the development of both general and specific physical qualities.

Keywords: comprehensive approach, methodological recommendations, biological and physiological processes, research, MHR (Maximum Heart Rate), lung vital capacity, recovery period, general and specific physical qualities, psychological preparedness.

Introduction: The structure of annual training and the methods and tools used in the process of preparing long-distance runners within a training group are being developed based on various scientific studies, practical research, and methodological recommendations. The annual training plan and its structure include all the necessary stages for preparing athletes throughout the year. In this process, training sessions are planned in advance and are structured based on the athletes' physiological characteristics, goals, and levels of preparedness. The physical development and readiness of long-distance runners are closely linked biological and physiological processes. This study presents and scientifically analyzes the results of research conducted on the physical development and preparedness of long-distance runners. Undoubtedly, long-distance running is considered one of the most fascinating and Olympic-recognized sports disciplines. Therefore, organizing this process and identifying talented and promising athletes from different regions has become one of the top priorities of our government's current effective policies.

Literature review. M. S. Olimov, N. T. To'xtaboyev, and G. S. Xo'jamkeldiyev conducted research on the preparation process of long-distance runners and achieved optimization of the training process. As we know, the distribution of the preparatory phases (such as the general preparation period, pre-competition period, and recovery phase) within the annual training structure plays a crucial role. These stages are coordinated with each other and are aimed at achieving high-level results. Modern training methodologies are used in annual training programs to prepare athletes, including interval training, specialized methods for long-distance

runners, and psychological preparation techniques. Currently, in order to increase the effectiveness of training methods, athletes' levels of preparedness are regularly measured using physiological and biochemical assessments. Improving the structure and methodology of annual training also places great emphasis on enhancing the skills and knowledge of coaches. For this purpose, participation in various seminars, exchanging experiences, and preparing scientific articles are actively promoted.

Discussion. The goals of the training sessions are determined based on the athlete's individual objectives. In the case of long-distance runners, special attention is given to increasing their physical strength, developing endurance, and effectively managing competition preparation and recovery processes.

The methodological tools used during the training period are crucial for studying the means and methods applied in preparing long-distance runners. Both aerobic and anaerobic training play a role, but aerobic physical loads are of primary importance in long-distance running. At the same time, anaerobic methods (such as interval and fartlek training) are used to enhance the athlete's endurance (Table 1).

Functional Indicators in Long-Distance Runners

Numb.	Physiological Indicators	Control group		Experiment group	
		BE	AE	BE	AE
1	Heart Rate (HR, beats per minute)	76,9±4,5	75,8±4,1	76,4±4,3	74,1±3,8
2	Breath-Holding Duration (Gerche test, seconds)	20,4±3,8	21,5±3,6	21,7±3,7	22,7±3,2
3	Maximal Oxygen Consumption (VO ₂ max, ml/min)	2894±196	3017±178	3045±181	3242±188
4	Lung Vital Capacity (LVC, ml)	2924±511	3224±459	3279±491	3895±465
5	Relative Lung Vital Capacity (RLVC, ml/kg)	56,1±4,9	57,8±4,3	58,4±5,4	61,2±4,4

Note: The training group of long-distance runners was analyzed based on special methodologies focused on competition preparation, with assessments conducted at the beginning and end of the research

Result. This table presents the pre- and post-research results of the long-distance runners from the training group. The research was primarily based on tests measuring heart rate, lung vital capacity, breath-holding duration, and maximal oxygen consumption (VO₂ max). The study focused on improving athletes' endurance and strength qualities through a specially developed annual training plan. Following the training camps conducted under this plan, the results of the experimental group showed significant improvement, as revealed through mathematical and statistical analysis.

Conclusion: Long-distance running is a sport that requires not only physical strength but also psychological resilience. This type of sport not only promotes a healthy lifestyle but also plays a significant role in helping student-athletes achieve success in competitions. Despite the clear necessity and logic of systematically using health-enhancing tools in the preparation of

qualified athletes, in practice, the issue of finding a rational balance between training loads and recovery measures remains a challenge and calls for further research.

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